

THE INFLUENCE OF MODERN EDUCATOR'S CREATIVE IMAGINATION ON THE DESIGN OF INNOVATIVE ONLINE LESSONS

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***Abstract.** In today's world of digital technology and globalization, the education system faces the need to adapt and implement innovative approaches to learning. Central to this process is the creative imagination of the teacher, capable of transforming traditional teaching methods, and improving the effectiveness of pedagogical communication, which includes the creation of innovative lessons in the online educational environment. Pedagogical "facilitation" should be considered and actualized as a skill of creative pedagogical communication, which will be an important criterion in the development of innovative training programs, and methodological manuals for students of pedagogical faculties and teachers.*

***Keywords:** creative imagination, pedagogical communication, teacher-facilitator, online environment, online lesson.*

The online educational environment represents a new paradigm of learning, the transition to online education was significantly accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, which revealed the need to develop and implement new forms of pedagogical communication. Despite the high rates of adaptation and development of online educational systems in the world, there is still a negative attitude of the pedagogical community towards this format of learning. This is due to concerns about the decrease in the quality of the educational process and the negative psychological aspects, such as the feeling of isolation in students. Insufficient interdisciplinary empirical research influences the pessimistic evaluation of the new

learning format. Also, the unwillingness of educators to study and use the necessary technical tools of the online educational environment leads to stagnation and a lack of proper attention to the peculiarities of online learning formats. At the moment there are synchronous, asynchronous, and mixed formats of online learning. Synchronous, asynchronous, and blended formats of online teaching have their unique advantages. They allow multidimensional construction of the educational process: it also provides direct interaction and social involvement, autonomy, uniting, and creating a balanced educational environment.

One of the main advantages of online education is the accessibility, flexibility of learning, and personalization of the learning process. It is possible to study from anywhere in the world at a time that is convenient for students, which is important for working professionals and those who live in remote areas. The individualization of the learning process provides the opportunity to repeat difficult material, receive individual assignments, and learn at your own pace. Nevertheless, M.A. Manokin, and E.A. Shenkman, considering the features of synchronous and asynchronous online learning, point out that only in the presence of special competencies of a modern teacher: the ability to work in the online environment and use its communication channels, teacher training in the field of psychology and communication culture, it is possible to build effective pedagogical communication in general [1, p.27].

One of the important competencies of a teacher in pedagogical communication is creative imagination, which is able not only to adapt new technologies and methods to educational practice but also to create innovative forms of teaching.

The role of the educator's imagination in pedagogical communication.

B. A. Slastenin emphasizes the peculiarity of the pedagogical profession and it consists in the fact that by its nature it is humanistic, collective, and creative [2, p.11].

The phenomenon of imagination presents a multifaceted challenge. Firstly, it is characterized by complexity and ambiguity in the definition of the term itself,

secondly, it requires the ability to distinguish from other cognitive functions such as memory, thinking, and perception, thirdly, it is necessary to explore more deeply the key aspects of imagination for effective pedagogical communication in the context of online education.

The creative imagination of a teacher is, first of all, openness to change and readiness to experiment with new teaching methods, internal motivation, and interest in using innovative teaching methods. V.T. Kudryavtsev writes that "imagining, a person as if immediately penetrates into the essence, into the basis of the developing integrity of the subject" [3, p.61].

Consider the key aspects of teacher imagination that influence the ability to design interactive lessons in an online environment.

Flexibility of thinking and innovation:

A teacher with a well-developed creative imagination has flexibility in thinking, which will allow for original adaptation of methods, and finding innovative approaches to teaching. The creative approach of a teacher helps to find unique and effective ways of solving complex problems. First of all, a teacher is an innovator who is better able to cope with uncertainty and make non-standard decisions in developing students' abilities to critically evaluate information and make decisions independently.

Cultural and social development:

In a global multicultural society, imagination helps the teacher to integrate cultural and social aspects into the learning process, making it more diverse and inclusive.

This fosters pupils' broad outlook and respect for different cultures and traditions.

Innovative thinking:

Imagination is the basis for innovative thinking, which is especially important in the modern educational context, which requires constant updating and the introduction of new technologies and methods. For modern students, it is not the

process of accumulating knowledge that is important, but the ability to apply this knowledge practically.

Facilitation and creativity in online lessons.

The term facilitation was introduced into pedagogy thanks to the works of the American psychologist Carl Rogers in the mid-twentieth century and had a significant impact on pedagogical theory and practice, especially in the context of the development of humanistic education. He suggested that the role of the teacher should be not so much authoritarian as supportive, creating conditions for students to learn and develop independently.

For the first time considering the facilitation style in pedagogy, Carl Rogers, especially emphasized the importance of a "person-centered" approach to learning, focusing on the active activity of the student [4, p.128].

In pedagogy, there are many different methods, techniques, and principles used to design lessons, which are designed to be creative, making learning a foreign language, for example, effective and fun. The techniques and methodologies used in the TESOL program are inherent to the facilitative style of teaching: "Desuggestopedia, Total Physical Response, Communicative Language Teaching, Concept Checking Questions (CCQ), Effective Seating Arrangement [5, p. 96-110].

The goal of the teacher-facilitator is to organize the effective work of the group without interfering with the meaningful context of work on the task. The facilitator operates with the group roles of participants and acts by setting group norms and rules of interaction. The facilitator uses various methods of organizing group work with clearly defined rules [6, p.95].

The use of a variety of facilitation techniques will allow for a creative approach to organizing group work, taking into account specific aims, objectives, and group dynamics and developing the necessary cooperation skills in students:

1. Brainstorming (Brainstorming, Reverse Brainstorming) is a method of idea generation where participants freely propose ideas without criticism, accepting any suggestions. It stimulates creativity, gathering a large number of ideas in a short period of time.

2. World Cafe is a method of moving between small groups to discuss different aspects of issues. An open environment is created to share knowledge and ideas, synthesizing and developing the discussions.

3. The Six Thinking Hats method was developed by Edward de Bon. Six different colored hats symbolize a particular way of thinking or six roles, which helps to explore a problem from different perspectives.

4. The case method is used to analyze and solve a real or hypothetical situation in order to find group solutions.

5. The group discussion method helps participants to discuss a particular topic together, and by exchanging opinions participants learn active listening skills.

6. A visual technique for group discussion is the Metaplan. Cards are used to fix a flipchart, and markers to structure the ideas and opinions of the students.

7. "Mind Mapping", "Fishbone Diagram", and "tag cloud" - visualizing ideas and their connections using diagrams and charts for the purpose of structuring and stimulating creative thinking.

One of the key ideas of the "facilitative" pedagogical style is to encourage independent learning, where each student is responsible for their own educational path, developing critical thinking and self-reflection skills. L.S. Vygotsky notes that the teacher has a new responsible role. He will have to become an organizer of the social environment, which is the only educational factor, and "the role of the teacher will grow immeasurably, it will require from him the highest examination of life so that he could turn education into the creativity of life" [7, p. 334].

Imagination will allow the teacher to find new ways to motivate students. Interactive lessons that include gamification and project-based learning increase the level of student engagement and make learning attractive and meaningful because of the important process of co-creation. Co-creation gives freedom and trust not only to other participants of the educational process but first trust and acceptance of oneself, freedom to express one's point of view and to accept another vision without evaluation.

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